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AN EXPLORATORY STUDY ON ETHICAL ASPECTS IN PARTICIPATORY RESEARCH ON RENEWABLE ENERGY

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Abstract: In this paper an approach to understand ethical issues in green energy innovation actions among participants in a research programme in a small island is presented. Issues related to the participation of citizens in research activities carried out under the frame of energy transition are explored directly with participants through interviews performed at the beginning of the research project. All island's participants on the project produced their opinions about communication in the project, implications for participating, responsibilities as volunteers, expectations. Also, insights about volunteers' perceptions on the project's management of privacy, personal data handling, social implications, ecological meanings, and engagement are explored. The paper highlights some different ethical issues not covered (or covered to an inadequate degree) in the academic literature which are facing stakeholders (particularly volunteers) in the renewable energy sector.

Keywords: *privacy, motivation, research, engagement, renewable*

CONTEXT

In recent years it has become evident that it is necessary to stop using fossil fuel as means to provide energy. This also applies more and more frequently to nuclear energy, that although it is not so directly related to climate change but must deal with the problem and dangers of nuclear energy waste management. A waste management problem not just for us, but also for future generations. As an alternative – and as a strategy of diversification – renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, tide, etc. are not just proposed but also used increasingly, and quite rightly promoted. However, there are certain aspects of the implementation of new energy models that we need to have a critical look upon. In the light of current climate emergency, can we afford the negative from certain sectors to comply with research demands that might led us to disaster? Are we again forcing people to accept activities and technology that otherwise would have probably refused to install in their homes? Are these people who collaborate heroes or are they just doing their duty? Or maybe are we prone to do so just by our own selfish interests? Sometimes we can even encounter that very awkward person that tries to hinder the advances in science for obscure motives, either by boycotting, not participating knowing their collaboration is needed, or other hampering actions, which at the end can be just personal attitudes towards fellow citizens, wrongly focussed, obviously.

From the provocative statement made by Goodman (1969) decades ago bringing to the field of moral philosophy scientific research and technology, very central aspects of modern civilization, to the recent approach by Sovacool (2013) on energy, it is clear that research in energy and renewable energies have a moral stand that cannot be obviated. As Goodman puts it there is no neutral moral ground from which technology can be developed, understood, implemented, or withdrawn. With specific reference to energy research, Sovacool (2013) observes that one cannot talk about building infrastructures, improving energy security, developing energy resources, forecasting future energy demands or conducting research on new technologies without first asking what this energy is for, what values and moral frameworks should guide us on these enterprises, including research but also who will be benefited or harmed. It is not just about the final product and developments; we must also think about the process.

The request/demand/requirement for the recognition of the fact that ethical considerations are ubiquitous and central to our human nature

must be recognized in energy research (Smith, J., & High, M. M. 2017). All the actors (volunteers, technicians, administrators, managers, etc.) are involved, whether they want to or not, with the ethical considerations that pervade all aspects of the research, and they all are responsible for those acts and decisions. The result will be colored with positive or negative values. We know that people make ethical judgments about the role of energy in societies that they imagine as 'good' or 'desirable' or more 'advanced', naturally analyzing all the variety of information, data and ideas -which sometimes are conflictive- regarding the energy they possess, thus outlining the conceptions that people have of energy in their environment and in their daily lives. The same way as how it is interpreted by Smith and High (2017) the embracing of the ethnographic gaze on energy ethics and the questions it arises about who we are listening to, and what can we expect from that analytical framework, we must consider, in a smaller scale, if we are listening to our volunteers in the research and how this communication can assure compliance with ethical standards and the identification of new ethical issues. As stated by Van Den Hoven, et al. 2017, institutional and technological design are all around us and they constitute part of our daily life. We live in highly designed and engineered environments where the processes that come to help the development of such design products is also important as these products can empower us as well as constrain us in particular ways. Thus, there are always ethical and moral implications in any technical development, and in the evaluation and testing of technical devices.

Other specific questions arose directly from considering emerging trends such as the creation of energy communities or the technical aspects associated with demand response. How can local decision makers and politicians, civilians, power companies, communities promote demand response? Do we really need to convince people to adopt green solutions for their energy needs when the current climate change emergency is so real? Is it ethical to do so? How can we help getting a greener future? What happens with local community energy management? What about economic issues? And which are the commitments taken by the electricity providers and network managements? If the whole system is controlled by an energy community there seems to be a close relation, however if it is not...what are the user feelings and expectations from members?

All these questions arose from the beginning of the project with the objective of achieving island energy independence through renewable energy generation and storage, a demand response platform, and promot-

ing user engagement in a local energy community. This study tries to contribute to this new knowledge demands by exploring the ethical aspects of this renewable energy project, and by exploring citizens' views on some ethical issues to help existing approaches. These tactics already take into consideration facts such as trends in globalization, digital revolution, or energy market liberalization in new energy systems (Chilvers et al. 2018), issues that account for these increasingly complex and diverse roles of the general public as well as individual citizens. The activities carried out in the island are supposed to pave the way for a more receptive attitude towards DR and other green energies solutions.

In order to apply proper demand response, it is necessary to install meters, and meters imply the consumption monitoring and thus data generating on consumption. That said privacy and security issues should be controlled and addressed. This might take several solutions, but we need to consider if users are happy with the lot: the data collection, data management and data analysis. Also, we must ponder the use of devices: some people might not want to use electronic devices and or don't have them (compliant with a zero energy waste policy on the other hand).

Leaving aside the problem of energy justice, that also affects green energy (Pellegrini et al. 2020, Lacey-Barnacle et al. 2020, Hatzakis et al. 2019) the study does neither focus on the ethics of energy transition. The study focusses on the issues related to participation on green energy research programs and the complication it can have for participants, society at large and the possible solutions provided for the scientific and research community. One thing is how change occurs and another one is how it should occur. The need for scientific and technical results drives us to test and validate our ideas and findings that come into direct contact with the general population at the time of testing and testing has its own complex idiosyncrasy and many factors to consider. As pointed by Damgaard (2021) citizens are viewed primarily as users and consumers of energy and not as voices that can direct this transition to clean energies. This approach needs to change. Participants -in a project that explores the use of clean energy in small communities- can be seen as a contribution and as a commitment to the installation of green practices, but there is more to it: we will explore other aspects that are related to the research activities. To our knowledge currently the research in ethics and renewable energies remain constricted to the role of the end-user, whether they are consumer or prosumers, and the emphasis on the connection between demand and supply. However, the study wanted to explore other aspects

that are also important and have not been fully explored. It is agreed with Damgaard that we all need to rethink how people “make sense of energy and energy transition in their daily lives”.

The paper does neither address the issue of the recently coined term energy ethics (Smith, & High, 2017) as this term is more related to the way in which energy affects our lives, societies and future and is also a concept complementary to energy justice, and not so much related to the research activities looked at in the project. However, it has in common the idea that it explores the multiple and varied ways in which people experience, conceptualize, and evaluate matters of energy in their lives.

Different philosophical perspectives tend to emphasize different factors as being ethically important, so thinking about an ethical issue from a variety of perspectives can alert us to considerations that we might have missed had we addressed it from a single perspective. When there is disagreement at a practical level, awareness of the philosophical perspectives underlying the competing views can help to identify what is at issue between them and to find grounds for agreement or compromise.

So, from a utilitarian approach Demand Response seems obviously a good action, but it needs to consider related issues that affect its perception somehow, how can you convince people to install the new technology? Does that mean that the cost should be assumed by the whole community when certain citizens can't afford the necessary implementation burdens, such as installation materials, devices and other costs?

McMullin (2018) says that “as we pursue our projects and desires, interact with others, and share public institutions and meanings, we are constantly shifting back and forth among these three practical perspectives, each bringing different elements of a situation to salience and highlighting different features of the world and our place in it as good or bad”. So, the question in green energy also relates to the way we want to be seen by our peers, how we intermingle and cooperate with others and what do we understand about higher social instances and the way in which we navigate along these lines of action.

Morality is the system through which we establish what is correct and incorrect behaviour, that is, the guide for a virtuous, noble, or at least correct behaviour. Moral theory describes how people, in their everyday actions and judgments, make decisions about what is right and what is wrong. Morals are the predominant standards of behaviour that allow people to live in society, since they provide patterns of behaviour that facilitate and guide coexistence. Morality often requires that people sac-

rifice their own short-term interests for the benefit of society. A good example is giving up personal wealth to help others in need. Ethical behaviour is tightly related to morals as both comprise sets of standards such as those incorporated in a code of ethics.

What about the implications on residents: who is going to control de place? This is an important question as it has a significant influence on the overall organization of the household members' everyday life, which is constituted by a complex of mutually dependent practices (Shove & Walker, 2014) such as cooking, showering etc. Who is the person in charge of accepting the participation in the research project and does she or he consult to the other dwellers concerning actions? Such changes in daily routines are difficult to imagine without processes of learning where householders try out, negotiate and gain experiences with new ways of doing things. The effects of this demands from the program to synchronize dwellers everyday domestics practices with the rhythms of power generation defines a set of energy ethics as expressed by Forde (2017).

According to Wilk (2009), unconscious habits and routines can be made visible to us and become subject to reflection through the process of *cultivation*. And the way for us to be aware of these unconscious habits can be through interaction with others that made us reflect upon them. So, if only one dweller is interacting with project stakeholders does that mean that maybe only this person can be made aware of his/her habits, or does it mean that this process gets extended to the other residents?

Royston (2014) demonstrated that changing how practices are performed necessarily involves developing new sets of embodied know-how on how to carry them out. Thus, education on the demand response and energy management seems to be pertinent among other actions.

Calls for the integration of ethics in the engineering and software -and not just for artificial intelligence- work environments have been emerging for a while (Zandvoort et al. 2000; El-Zein et al. 2008; Ocone, 2013). If we look at it carefully the conjunction of those desired ethical principles developed in the engineering and computing arenas with the better-established ethics awareness in social sciences, where living labs, co-creation and other methodologies have an important say, can assure that both the process and results are compliant with -at least sufficient- ethical standards and follow an ethical approach.

The aim of the project should always be to improve participants' conditions. This does not mean, however, that researchers in living labs environments assume that users have to be unpaid contributors, moti-

vated by the anticipation that their participation will solve their problems or lead to 'better' designs, as mentioned by Mulder et al. (2008). That is the case for the research project, but researchers should make sure to have tools at hand to mitigate possible adverse effects as those commented in the personal interviews.

Another important issue raised by Barcenilla & Tijus (2012) is that of ideas and their creator/s, what happens if a person doesn't want to share ideas that can benefit the project or the research of even just fellow participants?

There are other more delicate matters of difficult solution: in dealing with sustainability and fairness what about those that cannot participate in the project or research programme? What about those that cannot even access the opportunity to show fellow citizens how can they help in stopping green house effects? Are there some options that can be done and show empathy for this potentially frustrating situation?

We are faced to the need to provide energy services to society to allow its growth and development, but on the other hand this provision entails important distributional consequences from the economic point of view, access, and a significant environmental impact.

All of the foregoing analysis allows us to reflect that the ethical aspects of energy production and consumption arise basically from the decisions on energy matters that have to be established thinking about the way in which access to energy should be granted, and logically also thinking of development (in all aspects) but ideally oriented towards an economically viable, environmentally sound and socially acceptable way.

In this particular case, it seems that there would be no ethical problem intrinsic to the project's objectives of facilitating energy independence obtained through renewable energies in a small island. Exploring participants views tried to shed light on all these issues that permeate the debate on renewable energies and its ethical implications in the context of a research project.

METHODS FIELD STUDY: THE INTERVIEWS

To explore certain issues related to demand response some personal interviews were carried out in La Graciosa, a small island in the Canary Islands archipelago. Respondents were participants in the project, a project that tries to develop a technical and business model to demonstrate that its

objective of achieving island energy independence through renewable energy generation and storage, a demand response platform, and promoting user engagement in a local energy community can bring economic benefits, contribute to the decarbonisation of local energy systems, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and improve environmental air quality.

The interviews were conducted during the home installations of the solar teams. All interviewees participate in the project on a voluntary basis. An informative session was previously scheduled in order to recruit participants. The informative session was organized by representatives of the consortium in collaboration with the city council. The number of people interviewed amount to 15, which correspond to all project volunteers. It is only a small sample in a very small island, but it was hoped to get some insights on people's perception about the moral implications of being part of a research project as participants with responsibilities as well as rights.

Two informative sessions and other activities carried out in the island at the beginning of the project were conceived to promote consciousness about demand response, green energy, energy communities, etc., which in turn contribute to the "energy citizenship" proposed mentioned by Soeiro & Ferreira Dias (2020), which in turns encourage individuals to "contribute more broadly to the energy transition". It is known that to achieve good levels of engagement in the field of environmental management significant planning and exchange among researchers and stakeholders is required (Jasny et al. 2021). It is expected that achieving this much sought energy democratization serves to increase the level of acceptance of renewable energies. It is thus important to promote public activities where awareness is promoted on the local community about all these topics related to energy systems (Koirala et al. 2018).

During the interviews carried out under the project -they gave their written informed consent to be included in the study- it was unanimous that participants with installations been deployed in their homes were quite happy to participate and some even viewed it as a citizen duty.

It is necessary to reflect the difficulty in getting elaborated answers in the interviews. The reasons given were mainly two: the first referring to the population, it is a population with a high prevalence of elderly people who also do not feel comfortable at first with strangers (as the project workers were at first); trust comes later. The second reason is that many of them found the questions difficult to answer both due to the content and the generalized state of misinformation - not only about the project

but also about many aspects related to demand response, renewable energy, local communities. energy management, etc.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first question asked to all volunteers concerned privacy and data management by outsiders (see Annex 1). Except for one participant (“I want a discreet life without being part of statistics”) everyone else mentioned was quite happy with the data retrieval by external parts and its data analysis and management, it seemed to them “necessary”, “logical”, “that generates efficiency” in general, which is ultimately a necessary step that results in an improvement in the service.

Also, in question three -about consumer data facilitated by participants to strangers (project workers)- all interviewees perceived it as nothing to worry about and happy to provide such data: “It doesn’t bother me”, “No problem”. Most respondents to the questionnaire said that they were happy with the use of their home energy consumption data made available to the companies participating in the project. Data acquisition on energy consumption is one of the issues that usually trouble participants as found in Ranade & Beal, 2010, Hatzakis et al. 2019; however in our research it seemed that respondents did not care much about that, and they were quite aware of the need of such data acquisition for the project results. Some respondents assume there can be some risks and privacy breaches, but they did not seem to mind about data collection, perhaps because they are not aware of the fact that monitoring the energy consumption implies certain knowledge about their activities at home (such as showering, cooking or watching TV), data that are recorded. There is also another insight that might have been missed: if the data is used for improving the service and they refuse to consent about this monitoring then they lose the chance to be in the research programme and so eventually they are “forced” to assent and comply.

The second question refers to privacy in general in relation to the installations as well as home practices. Respondents saw it as a necessary step, and they were happy and willing to collaborate. However, the same person concerned about his anonymity (discreet way of life) also mentioned that: “Yes, it is uncomfortable for me if we continue to do surveys, but for the installation it is not annoying.”. Therefore, it must be assumed that the population in general are not bothered about the access to hous-

ing, implementation of technology, lifestyle, pets, etc. in general some tangential meddling in the lives of the inhabitants and new socio-technical practices (Forde, 2017).

Participants did not object to the batteries, meters, solar panels, etc., and did not consider access to its data -which was personal consumption- to be either dangerous or a pain.

However, it might be considered that these volunteers have been helping the project staff from the very beginning who, in addition to installing equipment in their homes, have participated in the design of the energy control system. Perhaps they feel obliged not only to participate and offer their space and time but also to adopt technologies even if they are not quite convinced. Can we talk about social pressure? How can researchers and technicians stop an uncomfortable participant that might wish to leave but is not strong enough to verbalise it?

What about citizen science programs that somehow forces us to accept (maybe) home installations and interferences that otherwise users would have not tolerated or not been comfortable with? Is it peer pressure again, coercive power, competition pressure from economic peers?

When the volunteers were asked about their knowledge of data protection regulations -both the European H2020 and GDPR and the national LOPD- only one person answered that they did not know it (“No, I did not know”). The majority answered that they knew about their existence but were not sure exactly about what they were, except that these laws refer to privacy: “I have heard about it, but I do not know exactly what it implies”, “I know of its existence, but I am completely unaware of the Data Protection Act”. A third of the respondents said they knew the law, but mostly referring to the Spanish LOPD*. It seems they were not concerned about this aspect of the research.

The participants in the project want and hope that the new technologies are facilitating and comfortable, but they accept that they can be ugly, that they can have some negative traits. This is minimized by the benefits these new technologies provide, including their infrastructures.

The fact that respondents were more than happy to participate in the project from the first contact shows that in the case of La Graciosa the “not in my yard” (Colmenares-Quintero, 2020) concept does not apply,

* Ley Orgánica 3/2018, de 5 de diciembre, de Protección de Datos Personales y garantía de los derechos digitales [Law 3/2018, of December 5th, Protection of Personal Data and guarantee of digital rights]

either as a community or as individual citizens. There is a genuine interest in renewable energies among the island population: it must be mentioned that some volunteers could not participate due to technical or administrative reasons although they were quite prone to do so.

There were four answers to the contribution aspect of participating in the project distributed as: Personal satisfaction (n9), Economic savings (n4), Environment (n4) and Doing something good (n4). These results are not dissimilar to a study carried out by Alender (2016) who found that the strongest motivators to participate in a citizen science project were helping the environment and contributing to scientific knowledge. This collaborative attitude is in line with Rawls's ideas (1971) about cooperation and not coercion where the so-called "sensible-reasonable citizens" want to live in a society where they cooperate with other citizens in conditions acceptable to all, and where it is also not intended to impose individual doctrine on others who are also willing to search for mutually agreeable rules and seeking the avoidance of coercive power whether it is social or individual.

To the popular response issued on the motivation to participate in the study consisting of "personal satisfaction" we should find the ulterior motivation that makes these people feel satisfied by collaborating in the research. Is it a personal satisfaction related to altruism? In direct relation to doing good? as four people responded. What exactly does that personal satisfaction indicate? It is probably due to a series of factors: this satisfaction is given by highly accepted social behaviours of collaboration with the group.

On the other hand, a respondent—probably someone more concerned about power cuts and energy pricing fluctuations—reflected about this aspect by stating that the contribution from the project was related to "security, to know that I am going to have some independence (from the grid) and that we are collaborating in something good".

When asked about their view on positive and negative aspects of participating on the project most answers were very positive and in relation to previous concerns. The negative aspects of participating in the project are related to the uncertainty in the execution times, the unexpected delays. It should be noted that these interviews were carried out during the COVID 19 pandemic, and the administrative and logistical aspects were subjected to delays – some of them more important than others. The only other negative aspect mentioned was related to the insistence on communication with the researchers and workers that carried out the installations, although it "compensates for the positive aspects of the project". Positive aspects were mentioned similarly to the answers in the previous question:

contribution to energy improvement, and environmental aspects, energy saving, collaborate in a better future, opening the way for its implementation (renewable energies) in all homes. In this sense, a very important mention to achieve the objectives of the project referred to “creating an association in the town for the improvement (of aspects of energy independence and clean energy) in the future “.

As for the reactions verbalized by the participants, it must be said that they were all very positive except for a somewhat peculiar one: one person expressed that she thought briefly about the “possibility that it was a hoax.”. This is not new as not trusting companies in the area of renewable energy have been already presented by Hatzakis et al. 2019. Thus, not even such respectable institutions as the EU, which partially subsidizes the project, can guarantee the trust of citizens. Other explanations for this possible mistrust may have its origin in the direct sources of information to which the possible participants had access: the local political authority (city council) and the consortium partners who presented the project in a public event. Unfortunately, the researcher did not delve into this question. The rest (eleven respondents, 73%) insisted that they wanted to participate from the very beginning as they saw benefits in economic terms, altruistic motives, environment and for the good of the community.

According to Liu et al. (2020) there are two dimensions of trust: competence-based trust which is linked to trust in the knowledge and expertise of responsible agents, and integrity-based trust linked to trust in honesty and transparency of responsible agents. Could this information mean that in this case the participant seemed to lack some of the integrity-based trust? It was a temporary feeling too so that might be interpreted as the fact that research suggest people find the decision-making process related to a concrete project more acceptable if the person trusts the responsible agent.

An attempt was made to explore whether the participants had ever felt pressured to participate in the project. Given the small size of the island and its small population, it was very important in the first contacts to ensure a certain interest in the project to later consolidate the participation of a minimum of residents in the project. The technical conditions and legal specifications were from the beginning a limitation to the possible number of participants that could be admitted to the study. Briefings and subsequent direct contacts with stakeholders were therefore essential. In general, the participants did not feel pressured at any time: neither before giving their acquiescence nor once the project started. It is true that one person reported that they felt pressured by electronic commu-

nication (“I feel pressured by e-mails and the insistence on signing contracts”) and another one that she felt pressure, but it was due to external agents to the project (“At the beginning of the project she felt pressured but due to personal circumstances”).

All participants consider that their participation in the project is important, and half of them believe that this relevance extends to the other participants. In this way, a certain group conscience and of the benefits of collaborating with each other for a common good is established, as one person clearly expressed “Of course, we all do great things together”.

This perception come into touch with the fact that ethical sensibility animates the everyday thoughts and practices of people, whether they work in renewables, nuclear energy, or fossil fuels; whether they work in industry, policy, or advocacy; whether they produce, distribute, or consume energy. Something we need to reflect about the distinction between the bright side and the dark side of our moral world and about the separation of the ethical from the political (Fassin, 2013).

CONCLUSIONS

There are several points emerging from the study:

- Double check proper representation of all stakeholders and significantly of those different belonging to a group (for example, all different consumer profiles should be represented, that includes those who belong to a minority), diversity among groups should be well represented
- GDPR, and privacy compliance, it is advisable to make sure participants are well informed and have access to all relevant documentation and if possible have simplified versions, for their better understanding
- Stay alert for possible “external” dangers (socio-economic changes, historical movements, media outlooks, representations, propaganda, political conflict, etc.) that can affect the development of the activities, and their effects on the relationship with participants
- Monitor relationships among stakeholders and participants: power relationships, communication styles, interaction patterns, etc.

The possibility should also be considered that certain people being awkward during all stages of the development. Those subjects can influence

initially interested parties, who might change their opinion considering the deeds of those interfering actors, actions that are not inherently critical but dubious or confrontational. If their attitude is damaging the confidence of other citizens in the works or planned activities, can these interferences be judged as pernicious? And in that case, are they morally wrong?

This lack of information was also mentioned as one of the barriers for adopters of sustainable energy together with high up-front costs, regulations, and more personal aspects such as trust -previously mentioned-, and risks awareness, social comparison, and opinion dynamics. Another issue that should not be underestimated is the psychological factors that affect energy consumption as mentioned by Itten et al. (2021) in reference to heating, for example. Those are important in conjunction with other various aspects to consider, and those challenges have to be addressed: economic, social psychological, technical and political.

Another important reality is that participants want to be informed but do not seem to know where to go apart from the obvious modern and easily available source: the internet. However, the group of elderly population do not tend to use this channel much. It seems pertinent to organize informative sessions to promote this knowledge not only among the participants but also among the rest of the residents. It became clear that an information campaign about all these important concepts is more than necessary for the advancement and understanding by citizens of concepts such as sustainable energy, energy self-sufficiency, energy communities, or active demand management. The need to promote awareness about energy transition and renewable energies through collective education exercises has also been reflected by Hiteva & Sovacool (2017).

Another area that researchers should be concerned about is the alignment of the project goals and activities with the interest of the participants (Alender, 2016). Leaving aside contractual obligations or normative procedures, if the original objectives of the project are modified during the process by the very sheer nature of research (Smith, & High, 2017) -as often happens in collaboration programmes, technical and scientific studies, living labs or citizens science for example-, then in what position the volunteer is left should be considered. Further research could be done in this area to see how the different changes and new actions are not imposed to the participant but rather negotiated in a way that comply with ethical standards and to make sure they are morally sound.

Finally, other consideration regarding the research processes and activities. All the project objectives are oriented towards renewable energies

and sustainability in general; however we must weigh up whether we are following a similar approach towards management, as the management of the project, management of the consortium and management and sustainability of the partners and stakeholders, especially volunteers, are also important components of the project. Are we consistent with such sustainable approach? How can we monitor that? Sustainable Project Management is the planning, monitoring and controlling of project delivery and support processes, with consideration of the environmental, economic and social aspects of the life-cycle of the project's resources, processes, deliverables and acts, aimed at realizing benefits for stakeholders, and performed in a transparent, fair and ethical way that includes proactive stakeholder participation (Silvius & Schipper, 2014). This is another ethical point that needs to be supervised.

The study tried to contribute to this new knowledge demands in the area of renewable energies by exploring the ethical aspects of a renewable energy projects by learning citizens views, even though it might not contribute to the defragmentation of the huge amount of knowledge been accumulated but hardly articulated and integrated. It could be seen that perceptions about data collection, data management and data analysis are something that, in general, does not concern participants, and in any case the perceived benefits of the participation on the project compensate for such loss of privacy.

The methodological limitations of a case study design make it difficult to extrapolate the findings toward a larger sample. Therefore, this paper focuses on making an in-depth analysis rather than making general claims. However, the insights regarding how participants felt pave the way for future validation on a larger scale and suggest future research directions.

However, there are a few recommendations that can be extracted from the study and previous research. integrity based trust is more important on project acceptability than competence-based trust, thus the moral side of the companies participating in a project must be highlighted and this can be seen on the brief doubts expressed by one participant. Before any action is taken by the researchers, the presentation of the stakeholders to volunteers must have this fact in mind and act accordingly.

The perceptions that the users have as a community (Colmenares-Quintero, 2020) of the relationship between accepting renewable energies based on natural sources as the sun, wind etc. -that also can have a different relationship and ancestral meanings for the community- were not explored in this study. These ancestral cultural perceptions and beliefs are

different from the modern approach where we consider those natural elements as natural resources, scrapped from any cultural, magical, social, cosmogonic, common heritage, collective imaginariu or tribal meaning. Could this be something relevant for residents in a small island?

FURTHER RESEARCH

There are several points that might be further explored in the area of renewable energies in relation to ethical issues arising from its research and implementation activities.

It could be interesting to explore that, given the fact that the smart meters can control the activities carried at home, such as cooking, taking a shower or watching TV, certain privacy issues arise from the installation of the smart meters, as the information is private and reflects on personal activities.

In the future the feelings of those that could not enter the project for technical or administrative reasons could be explored. Also, the effects of not been selected or included in a research programme that can potentially benefit participants, and in that sense what can we discover about discrimination, or positive discrimination for those less favoured, should be explored. Those affected by a rejection must not be unaware of how this decision was made and who were involved in this decision. Transparency in the notification and selection procedure seems to be an utmost need.

Another area to explore is related to further channels and motivations for engagement. How can stakeholders encourage the uptake of renewable solutions without been coercive?

Although all participants in the research project answered the survey, we understand that the size is small. However, as this is an exploratory study the information gathered is relevant considering that the data sample included the whole study population and the reduced population of the island. Further research should consider extending the survey to the population that did not participate in the research project and adapt the questions to a more general approach to ethics in renewable energies.

Exploring the effect of peer pressure as well as pressure administered can lead to better understand both rejection as well as approval of activities in the sector, nor just implementation of the technical solutions but also previous necessary research and innovation activities.

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